

Influence of Nationality Diversity on Financial Performance of Listed Commercial Banks in the Nairobi Stock Exchange

Lyma Kivali Mwangi¹, School of Business and Economics, Kenya Methodist University

Moses Kithinji², School of Business and Economics, Kenya Methodist University

Wilson Muem³, School of Business and Economics, Kenya Methodist University

Corresponding Author: Lyma Kivali Mwangi¹

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Abstract: This study sought to determine the influence of nationality diversity on the financial performance of commercial banks listed on the Nairobi Securities Exchange (NSE). Anchored on the Group Diversity Theory, the study emphasized the importance of heterogeneous boards in shaping strategic decisions, fostering innovation, and enhancing organizational outcomes. A descriptive research design was adopted, targeting all 12 listed commercial banks through a census approach to ensure comprehensive coverage. Secondary data was obtained from audited financial statements and corporate governance reports spanning the period 2021 to 2023. Key variables included the proportion of non-local directors on bank boards and financial performance measured using return on assets (ROA). Data was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques. The findings revealed a strong and significant relationship between nationality diversity and financial performance, with an R-square value of 0.900, a beta coefficient of 2.034, and a p-value of 0.001. This implies that increasing the representation of non-local directors substantially improves the financial performance of listed commercial banks. The study concludes that nationality diversity contributes positively to board effectiveness by bringing global perspectives, enhancing risk management, and strengthening corporate governance structures. It recommends that Kenyan commercial banks adopt policies that encourage the integration of both local and foreign directors, while regulators should provide guidelines on achieving an optimal balance to maximize value creation. These findings provide critical insights for policymakers, regulators, and bank executives on the strategic importance of board composition in driving sustainable financial performance.

Key Words: Nationality Diversity, Financial Performance, Listed, Commercial Banks, Nairobi Stock Exchange

Introduction

National diversity is important as it fosters innovation and enhances decision making across different sectors in the economy. The diversity in the financial sectors offers opportunities to people who were traditionally underrepresented thus helping in economic diversification. According to Beji et al. (2021) national diversity entails the presence of people from different countries within the economy with the aim of offering goods and services to the citizens. National diversity in the financial markets is critical in the performance of any economy as it ensures equitable access to resources and opportunities for all (Odero & Egessa, 2023). Financial diversity in the financial markets also leads to financial inclusion of all people in the economy as it helps the companies to take advantage of the inclusive culture and diverse society that is present in the country.

Globally, the national diversity has been critical in the performance of commercial banks which then lead to sustained economic growth and development. Commercial banks in different countries such have leveraged on national diversity to leverage on globalization and the rapid technological progress (Ding & Riccucci, 2023). In the USA, for instance, the commercial banks are designed to take advantage of the multicultural markets and diversified labor markets to target the untapped customer base. The US commercial banks achieve the national diversity through their board diversities to cater for the diverse nature of the USA market (Issa et al., 2022). These banks have been able to serve the needs of the businesses thus making immense contribution on the economic growth and development. In the UK, the national diversity helps the commercial banks. In the UK, the banks ensure that the economy has a stable financial system (Hosny & Elgharbawy, 2022). The national diversity in the country helps the banks to maintain the right balance in the board of governance to cater for all the needs of the people in the country.

In Africa, commercial banks act as intermediaries and plays crucial role in economic development by accepting deposits, offering credit and facilitating payments. In Nigeria, for instance, banks offer financial advice to individuals, businesses and government (Aziokwe & Okegbe, 2024). The country has a rich combination of diverse banks that illustrates the diversity in the country's economy. The banks have leveraged I the diversity of their workforce and their board members to foster a culture of innovation and creativity which enables them to add value to all sectors of the economy. The national diversity in the Nigerian banking sector helps diversify their operations

and cushion them against financial and other risks. In Ghana, the banking sector regulates supervises and directs the banking credit systems and ensure there is smooth operations. The banks control the financial systems in Ghana and through their financial intermediation and control a larger portion of investment (Mensah, 2020). The national diversity of the banking sector in Ghana ensures that there is technology exchange from different nations thus ensuring sustained growth.

Commercial banks in the Kenyan economy play a crucial role in the development of the economy as they avail the resources needed for growth. The commercial banks mobilize the savings in the country, finance businesses and facilitate trade in the economy (Nyakeyo, Mulwa, & Janet, 2025). These entities also offer various financial services such as managing payments, handling the collection of payments and assisting with investment policies by the government. The banking sector in Kenya is controlled by the Central Bank of Kenya (CBK) which controls the operations of the commercial banks (Gachoka, 2021). The country has a total of 43 banking institutions as of 2023 whereby about 40 of them are privately owned and three publicly owned. About 25 of these banks are owned by Kenyans while 15 of the banks are foreign owned indicating the nationality diversity in the Kenyan banking sector (Njoki & Nyamute, 2023). These commercial banks perform an essential role in the growth and development of the Kenyan economy by accepting deposits, processing payments and issuing if credit.

The banks in Kenya are agents of economic development as they create the right atmosphere for economic investments. These institutions have also played a crucial role in economic diversification by offering loans for agricultural production which is critical for Kenyan economic growth and development (Kiptum, Koske, & Limo, 2021). The banks offer credit for mechanized farming, marketing of products and land development thus enhancing agricultural production. Besides, the banks have been critical in the growth and expansion of the manufacturing sector by offering capital for acquisition of assets. The Kenyan commercial banks have contributed immensely towards job creation as they offer incentives to entrepreneurs enabling them to take loans for business expansion which leads to economic diversification.

Statement of the Problem

The importance of the commercial banks in the Kenyan sector cannot be overemphasized as they help individuals to accumulate savings and make these funds available for investments. Similarly, these banks offer credit services and buy investment securities to help diversify the economy. The

Kenyan commercial banks facilitate both internal and international trade through exchange rates and accepting bills of exchange (Omware, Atheru, & Jagongo, 2020). Thus, they help manage the control of capital on and outside of the country ensuring economic development. Foreign-owned institutions play a critical role in ensuring that the banking sector in Kenya is able to achieve its goals. These institutions help in capital flow and technology exchange between countries which is very critical for the development of the Kenyan banking sector.

Despite the growing presence of the national diversity in the Kenyan banking sector, characterized by several multinationals, the specific influence of these national diversity is underexplored. Broader studies have shown mixed findings whereby the Kenyan regulatory framework ensures diversity in the board of governance within the banks rather than in the whole industry (Nyakeyo, Mulwa, & Janet, 2025). Few studies have sought to examine the impact of nationality diversity on the performance of commercial banks, with most of the studies focusing on board composition on the performance of commercial banks in different parts of the world. For instance, Khan, Kamran, and Imran, M. (2020) examined the role of board composition on the commercial banks' performance in Pakistan. Gwaison and Maimako (2021) studied the impacts of board composition on the performance of selected commercial banks in Nigeria while Manyaga, Muturi, and Oluoch (2020) explored how board diversity influences investment opportunities in the commercial banks in Kenya. None of these studies focused on the impact of nationality diversity on the financial performance of commercial banks, which presents a research gap which this study seeks to fill. As such, this study will examine the Influence of Nationality Diversity on Financial Performance of Listed Commercial Banks in the Nairobi Stock Exchange

Research Objective

To determine influence of Nationality Diversity on Financial Performance of Listed Commercial Banks in the Nairobi Stock Exchange.

Hypothesis

H₀₁: Nationality Diversity has no significant influence on Financial Performance of Listed Commercial Banks in the Nairobi Stock Exchange

Theoretical Review

Group Diversity Theory

This theory was introduced by Kurt Lewin in 1945 and seeks to explain the changes that occur due to interactions in the group. At its core, this theory exposes the behaviors, forces and the interactions within the groups (Shore & Chung, 2022). It explains how the individuals within the groups interact and influence each other and how these interactions influence the functions of the group as a whole. This theory focuses in the group behaviors rather than focusing on the individuals and entails the communication models within the group, the social influence if the group and the decision making due to interactions of the group (Bernstein et al., 2020). This theory states that the group dynamics are critical for the success of a whole system. Besides, the theory states that differences in members such as demographic characteristics, cultural differences and cognitive differences are major influencers of the performance of an organization.

According to the group diversity theory, group composition like culture, nationality and ethnic background can be a major source of competitive advantage of a firm if well utilized. However, the same can also hinder group functioning if the organizational leaders due to not understand how to leverage on diversity (Duchek, Raetze, & Scheuch, 2020). This diversity in the group can lead to more innovation and creativity because the people from different backgrounds bring varied perspectives in the organizations. Consequently, the diversity increases the organization's problem-solving skills and increases competitiveness in the financial sector.

This theory is critical in this study as it explains the impact of nationality diversity on the performance of listed commercial banks in NSE. The listed banks in the NSE operate in a multicultural landscape which consist of both multinational and locally-owned banks. Besides, the banks operate in a highly volatile market that requires firms to innovate to overcome these inherent market risks. This theory explains that the diversity in the commercial banks can enhance decision making processes and increase the efficiency in risk assessments ((Ding & Riccucci, 2023). The diversity of the banking sector helps firms to adapt to the market dynamics because they have a broader global insight. Besides, the theory will help reduce group think and enhance innovation through the nationality diversity which brings diverse management skills on the banking sector.

Empirical Review

Different researchers have studied the impact of nationality diversity on the performance of firms in different sectors. Vullings and Dóci (2020) examined the impact of nationality diversity on the performance of global software development teams. The study collected data from 247 software development teams whereby temporal dispersion and leadership roles were examined. The data was collected using questionnaires whereby a stratified sampling method was used. The data was analyzed using SPSS and presented using tables and charts. The study noted that nationality diversity has a positive impact on performance. However, the study also noted that nationality diversity can lead to low performance if the leaders do not engage in supervision roles. The results revealed that diversity in the organization leads to more innovation and creativity which creates a competitive advantage in an organization. The main limitation of this study is that it done in another country thus posing a contextual gap in the current study.

Raithel, van Knippenberg, and Stam (2021) examined the impact of team leadership and cultural diversity on performance. The study identified leader cultural background, and the leader team tenure as the research variables. A systematic literature review was used in this study whereby articles and journals were used to examine the research topic. Content analysis was employed to identify the key findings from these studies after which narratives were used to present the results. The study noted that team nationality diversity has a more positive impact on performance if the leaders are foreign to the host country. It was also noted that leaders' cultural background has a positive impact on performance for leaders with short tenures. Importantly, this study states that nationality is a double-edged sword that can also lead to negative impacts if used wrongly. The main limitation of this study is that it was done in Indonesia which has a different legal and economic conditions compared to Kenya. Consequently, the results cannot be used to make a generalized conclusion on the current topic.

Wirawan and Willim (2023) explored how board diversity affect the financial performance of commercial banks. The study used age, gender, and nationality diversity whereby 9 commercial banks were targeted. A multilinear regression model was used in this study whereby the data was analyzed using SPSS. the results revealed that age and gender have a significant impact on the performance of commercial banks in Java while gender has an insignificant impact on performance. However, it was noted that all these variables affect the performance if they are used simultaneously. The main limitation of this study is that it was done in the commercial banks in

Indonesia which operate under a different regulatory framework. As such, the results from this study cannot be used to make a generalized conclusion on this topic.

Issa et al. (2021) studied the impact of board diversity on the performance of commercial banks in MENA countries. The study focused on nationality, gender and educational level as the variables for diversity. The sample consisted of 11 countries drawn from the MENA region. The research design entailed a generalized method of moments estimation on the data of banks listed in MENA countries between 2011 and 2018. The data was analyzed using SPSS and presented using tables and charts. The ordinary least squares, fixed and random effect techniques were used to support the robustness of the results. The results revealed that there is a significant relationship between board diversity and financial performance in commercial banks. The results also showed that gender and educational level diversity have insignificant impact in the performance of commercial banks. Although this study was done in the banking sector, it cannot be generalized in the current research because it was done in the MENA region which has a different economic model compared to Kenya.

Arnaboldi et al. (2020) investigated how board diversity and CEO background impacts the performance of commercial banks in the UK. The study used a sample of 54 banks in the UK that were publicly listed between 2004 and 2018. The study used the static and the dynamic modelling framework to identify the individual's specific effects on performance. The results revealed that there is a positive relationship between education background and the performance of commercial banks, although this relationship is insignificant. It was also noted that there is a positive significant association between gender diversity and the bank's performance. The study noted that nationality diversity has a negative impact on performance of the commercial banks. The main limitation of this study is that it was done in the UK whose banking sector is different from the Kenyan. Consequently, the results from this study cannot be used to make a generalized conclusion on the current research topic.

Methodology

The study applied a descriptive research design because it does not manipulate the study variables, therefore enabling the researcher to test the variables relationship under their natural circumstance. The study population for the study representing the unit of analysis was the 12 Nairobi stock exchange listed commercial banks, with the banks that were operational between 2021 and 2023

being included. The study applied a census sampling method where all the 12 banks were considered in the study.

A secondary data collection schedule was used for obtaining secondary data from the audited and published financial statements of the banks which were readily available in the Nairobi stock exchange and the central bank of Kenya. The annually reports for the three years were considered, between 2021 and 2023, on the return on the assets. Additionally, the websites for the companies were reviews to determine the nationality composition of the board of directors (both local and international board of directors).

Data that was obtained was cleaned sorted and entered into SPSS for analysis. Both descriptive and inferential analysis were used in data analysis. Included for descriptive analysis were mean, standard deviation, maximum and minimum values determination for the proportions of the nationality and the return on investment for the 12 firms. On the inferential analysis both correlation and inferential analysis were carried out to tests relationship between the variables as significance level of 0.05. Results were presented on tables and narrations done for interpretation and discussion purposes.

Results and Discussions

Descriptive Statistics

Results showed that the firm with the highest proportion of non-locals was at 0.49 indicating about 49% of non-locals in that company whereas the firm with the lowest proportion had 0.28 indication a 28% of the total number of non-locals in the board, on average the proportion of the non-locals in the board was 0.3925 indicating about 39.25% of non-locals in the board. On the dependent variable (return on assets), results revealed that the firm with the highest ROA had 0.81, whereas the firm with the lowest ROA registered 0.39, on average the listed commercial banks registered an industrial average of 0.5856 which shows a moderate financial performance (table 1)

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic
Nationality proportion	36	.21	.28	.49	.3925	.05173
Return on Assets	36	.42	.39	.81	.5856	.11088

Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis conducted between Nationality Proportion and financial performance revealed that Nationality diversity had a positive and significant correlation ($r=0.949$, $p\text{-value}=0.000$) with financial performance of commercial banks listed at NSE because the computed p -value of 0.000 was below the critical value of 0.05 (table 2). Similar findings by Vullingsh and Dóci (2020), in their study of global software development teams, similarly found that nationality diversity enhances innovation, creativity, and competitive advantage, thereby improving performance. The results opined that effective governance structure helps in enhancing organizations performance. Raithel, et al. (2021) also agreed with the findings that leaders with foreign cultural backgrounds where foreign directors are keen on boosting performance of banks through their expertise.

Table 2: Correlations Matrix

Correlations Matrix

		Nationality Diversity	Financial performance.
Nationality Diversity	Pearson Correlation	1	.949**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	36	36
Financial performance.	Pearson Correlation	.949	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	36	36

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Regression

Results of the model summary showed an R-square of 0.900 (table 3), which indicates that 90% of the changes in the financial performance of listed commercial banks at NSE can be explained by the nationality diversity (proportion of non-locals in the board).

Table 3: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.949 ^a	.900	.897	.03551

a. Predictors: (Constant), Nationality Proportion

Results also showed an F-ratio of 307.157 and a p-value of 0.000 (table 4) which indicated that the bivariate regression model was statistically significant in prediction of the financial performance of NSE listed commercial banks because the critical value of 0.000 was below the critical value of 0.05.

Table 4: ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.387	1	.387	307.157	.000 ^b
	Residual	.043	34	.001		
	Total	.430	35			

a. Dependent Variable: ROA

b. Predictors: (Constant), Nationality Proportions

Lastly results on the regression revealed a beta coefficient of 2.034, a t-statistic value of 17.526 which was also associated with a p-value of 0.001 indicating that a one-unit increase in national diversity (increase in the number of non-locals in the board), significantly led to a 2.034 increase in the financial performance of listed commercial banks at the NSE. Therefore banks with more diverse nationality are more likely to experience better performance. Results also indicated that constant in the model was significant because the computed p-value of 0.000 was below a critical value of 0.05. Holding other factors constant the financial performance was at -0.213. The study therefore rejected the null hypothesis that claimed nationality diversity does not significantly influence financial performance of listed commercial banks at the NSE.

Similar, findings were revealed by Issa et al. (2021), who studied banks in the MENA region, reported a significant overall relationship between board diversity and financial performance. However, Arnaboldi et al. (2020), who examined UK commercial banks, found nationality to be having negative though significant effect on financial performance, the divergent findings could be as a result of banking sector contexts difference in the two countries where presence of diverse nationalities in the Kenyan commercial banks could foster innovation, strengthen corporate governance and lead to better financial outcome. The final model can therefore be written as follows:

$$Y = -0.213 + 2.034X_1$$

Table 5: **Coefficients**

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.213	.046		-4.630	.000
	Nationality Proportions	2.034	.116	.949	17.526	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Return on Assets

Conclusions and Recommendations

The study established that nationality diversity has a strong positive and significant influence on the financial performance of commercial banks listed at the NSE. This underscores the value of diverse boards in bringing global perspectives, skills, and networks that enhance strategic decision-making. Unlike some studies in developed markets, the Kenyan context shows that nationality diversity can be leveraged as a strength rather than a challenge. It is therefore recommended that commercial banks in Kenya should actively embrace board nationality diversity as a governance strategy to improve competitiveness and performance. Regulators and policymakers should also encourage inclusive board structures that balance local and foreign expertise, while ensuring that effective leadership and supervision mechanisms are in place to minimize potential coordination challenges.

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